

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№6(1)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 284 sahifa,
1-iyun, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

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“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
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reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
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Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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MECHANISMS FOR ASSESSING ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS IN THE FINNISH EDUCATION SYSTEM AND THE POSSIBILITY OF THEIR ADAPTATION IN SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes modern mechanisms for assessing student achievement in the Finnish education system, in particular, the specific aspects of formative and summative assessment methods. The Finnish experience highlights the effectiveness of student-centered assessment, an individual approach, teacher freedom, and a stress-free control system. The possibilities of adapting these assessment mechanisms to the practice of secondary schools in Uzbekistan, existing problems, and promising solutions are also scientifically substantiated. The results of the study are important for improving the quality of education and improving the assessment system.

Key words: assessment mechanisms, formative assessment, summative assessment, student achievement, innovative approach, pedagogical experience, individual approach.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Finlyandiya ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilar yutuqlarini baholashning zamonaviy mexanizmlari, xususan, formativ va summativ baholash usullarining o'ziga xos jihatlari tahlil qilingan. Finlyandiya tajribasi o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan baholash, individual yondashuv, o'qituvchi erkinligi hamda stresssiz nazorat tizimining samaradorligini namoyon etadi. Shuningdek, ushbu baholash mexanizmlarini O'zbekiston umumta'lim maktablari amaliyotiga moslashtirish imkoniyatlari, mavjud muammolar va istiqbolli yechimlar ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari ta'lim sifatini oshirish hamda baholash tizimini takomillashtirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: baholash mexanizmlari, formativ baholash, summativ baholash, o'quvchilar yutuqlari, innovatsion yondashuv, pedagogik tajriba, individual yondashuv.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются современные механизмы оценки достижений учащихся в системе образования Финляндии, в частности особенности методов формативного и суммативного оценивания. Финский опыт демонстрирует эффективность личностно-ориентированного оценивания, индивидуального подхода, педагогической автономии учителя и системы контроля, свободной от излишнего стрессового воздействия. Также научно обоснованы возможности адаптации данных механизмов оценивания к практике общеобразовательных школ Узбекистана, существующие проблемы и перспективные пути их решения. Результаты исследования имеют важное значение для повышения качества образования и совершенствования системы оценивания.

Ключевые слова: механизмы оценивания, формативное оценивание, суммативное оценивание, достижения учащихся, инновационный подход, педагогический опыт, индивидуальный подход.

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalization process, improving the education system and increasing its quality is one of the main tasks facing the countries of the world. In particular, organizing the student assessment system based on modern requirements is recognized as an important factor determining the effectiveness of education. The experience of developed countries shows that the assessment process should not only serve as a means of control, but also serve to increase the student's motivation to learn, develop free thinking, and bring out individual abilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Finland, one of the countries that has achieved high results in the global education system, stands out for its quality of education, innovative approaches, and the effectiveness of its student assessment mechanisms. In this country, assessment processes are student-centered, focusing on the psychological state of students, the pace of individual development, and practical skills as key criteria. Finnish schools place great emphasis on formative assessment, ongoing analysis, and teacher observation, rather than traditional testing and strict control. This will help to create a stress-free learning environment for students and improve the quality of education.

In recent years, the education system of Uzbekistan has also implemented large-scale reforms to modernize assessment mechanisms based on international standards. In particular, new systems are being developed to implement a competency-based approach, participate in international assessment programs, and develop students' practical skills. In this regard, studying the Finnish experience and adapting it to the national education system is of significant scientific and practical importance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this article is to analyze the mechanisms for assessing student achievement in the Finnish education system and to highlight the possibilities of adapting them to the practice of secondary schools in Uzbekistan. Also, in the course of the study, the existing problems in the assessment system, advanced pedagogical experiments and promising solutions are scientifically substantiated.

The delegation of heads and professors of 10 pedagogical universities of Uzbekistan, carried out after 2020, focused on an in-depth study of the Finnish educational system, during which the experience of educational institutions such as the University of Jyväskylä was studied. As a result of these trips and studies, it was noted that the Finnish education model had a direct impact on the amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". This article is devoted to the analysis of the basic principles of the Finnish education system, approaches to assessing students' knowledge, and the factors of its success. The possibilities, advantages, and potential limitations of adapting the Finnish experience to the practices of improving the general secondary education system and assessing student knowledge in Uzbekistan are also discussed in a scientific manner.

Today, the Finnish education system is recognized as one of the most effective and advanced in the world. The success of the education of this country largely depends on the humane, fair and developing mechanisms for assessing the knowledge of students. The main goal of assessment in Finnish schools is not to punish or sort the student, but to support their individual development.

The assessment process in the Finnish education system is student-centered, taking into account each student's abilities, interests, and rate of development. In primary schools, the traditional numerical grading system is almost never used. Mainly verbal descriptive assessment methods are used. This reduces unnecessary pressure and fear in students and increases their interest in learning.

Finnish schools have a 10-point grading system, but until grade 7, students are only given verbal grades: below average, satisfactory, good, excellent. There is no form of assessment in grades 1 and 3. All schools in Finland are connected to the state electronic system "Wilma", which is an electronic school diary, and each parent has a personal code to access the electronic system. Teachers provide grades, attendance, and information about the student's school performance; Also, "future teachers", social workers, psychologists, and paramedics can get the necessary information here. In Finnish schools, students are not worried about the grades they receive.

The grounds of the schools are not fenced, nor are the overseers at the entrance to the school. The entrance gate of most schools has an automatic system, and the building is accessible on the basis of a schedule of classes. In warm weather, classes are often held outdoors, in parks, or on specially equipped patios.

Formative assessment plays an important role in the Finnish experience. Formative assessment is a type of assessment that is carried out regularly in the educational process, which helps to determine to what extent the student is mastering knowledge and eliminate existing shortcomings. The teacher monitors the student's performance, provides individual recommendations, and develops independent work skills. As a result, the assessment process becomes a developmental mechanism rather than a control tool.

In addition, teachers in Finnish schools are given great pedagogical freedom. Teachers can freely choose assessment criteria based on the students' level of preparation and needs. This ensures flexibility in the educational process. The assessment focuses primarily on practical tasks, projects, creative work, and team work results, rather than tests.

In recent years, significant reforms have been implemented in the Uzbek education system to improve assessment mechanisms. In particular, special attention is paid to assessing students' knowledge based on a competency-based approach, integrating into international assessment programs, and introducing innovative teaching methods. In this regard, studying the Finnish experience and adapting it to the national system is of great scientific and practical importance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

First of all, it is advisable to widely introduce a formative assessment system in schools in Uzbekistan. Because the traditional assessment system is more focused on determining the final result, formative assessment allows for continuous monitoring of a student's progress in the learning process. This helps students develop their free thinking, analytical approach, and creative abilities.

In addition, it is important to take into account the psychological state of students during the assessment process. The Finnish experience places great emphasis on creating a stress-free learning environment. It is also necessary to create a system of assessment that does not put excessive pressure on students, but rather encourages and motivates them, in schools in Uzbekistan.

It is also considered one of the important tasks to increase teacher professional competencies in assessment. In Finland, educators have a high level of experience and are able to freely apply assessment techniques. Therefore, in Uzbekistan, special attention should be paid to modern assessment methods in the system of retraining and advanced training of teaching staff.

However, it is important not to completely move the Finnish experience, but to adapt it to the national mentality, today's educational conditions and curricula. Because the educational system of each country has its own social, economic and cultural characteristics. Therefore, it is advisable to select and gradually implement the most effective aspects of the Finnish experience.

Overall, studying the assessment mechanisms in the Finnish education system will serve as an important factor in modernizing the education system of Uzbekistan, fairly and effectively assessing student knowledge, and improving the quality of education.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The mechanisms for assessing student achievement in the Finnish education system are characterized by being based on the principles of humanism, individuality, and a developmental approach. The main goal of assessment in this system is not to control the student, but to support his learning process, develop his free thinking, and increase his motivation to learn. Formative assessment, teacher autonomy, and a stress-free learning environment are particularly important factors in ensuring the effectiveness of the Finnish education system.

The results of the study show that adapting some effective aspects of the Finnish experience to the practice of general education schools in Uzbekistan is of great importance in improving the quality of education. This includes the widespread introduction of formative assessment systems, taking into account the individual characteristics of students, using motivating assessment methods, and developing the assessment competencies of teachers.

At the same time, when introducing foreign experience into the national education system, it is necessary to take into account the social, economic and cultural characteristics of the country. It is advisable not to completely move the Finnish experience, but to introduce it in stages, choosing the most effective elements.

Therefore, studying advanced assessment mechanisms in the Finnish education system and adapting them to Uzbek schools will serve to fairly assess students' knowledge, improve the effectiveness of education, and form a competitive education system that meets international educational standards.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №6(1)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.